

By Alan Hildrew & Paul Giller

2nd Edition, Oxford University Press
London, 480 pp.

Online ISBN: 9780191826139

Print ISBN: 9780198516101

€49.99

Since the publication of *The Ecology of Running Waters* by H.B.N. Hynes in 1970 (Liverpool University Press, Liverpool, England), which arguably invented the field of contemporary stream and river ecology, flowing water ecosystems have been the focus of several excellent undergraduate- and graduate-level textbooks. Hildrew & Giller have contributed to these by producing a remarkably fresh and comprehensive overview of historical and modern developments in stream and river ecology.

This attractively bound book consists of 10 chapters, numerous high-resolution figures, and 15 “topic boxes” providing authoritative vignettes of selected aspects of flowing-water ecology. Chapters 1-3 (Rivers

as ecological systems, Habitat templet, River biota) provide a solid introduction to the physical habitat templet, the natural flow regime, and the organisms found in streams and rivers. Although these chapters are all generally very good, the treatment of fluvial geomorphology and hydraulics seemed perhaps too elementary, with key processes, such as the relationship between near-bed hydraulics and the return interval of storm flows with the maintenance of habitat structure and channel form not being effectively integrated. On the other hand, the comprehensive treatment of non-fish vertebrates (e.g., birds & mammals) was both excellent and welcome.

The book really begins to shine, however, with Chapter 4 (Matching the habitat templet) which focuses on organismal adaptations to flowing water. In particular, I found the discussion of body form and the use of silk to be fascinating. In Chapters 5-7 (Population ecology, Living communities in rivers and streams, Species interactions and food webs), Hildrew & Giller provide an excellent review of population and community ecology. Notable sub-sections include a comprehensive expose of the tension between downstream drift and

population persistence, migration and mobility, the dynamics of “open populations”, and disturbance. A focus on climate change and intermittent streams, here and elsewhere in the book (e.g., Chapter 10), was particularly welcome as was the realistic critique of the current state of “species-trait analysis”, once thought to be a panacea for problems associated with purely taxonomic approaches; throughout these chapters Hildrew & Giller illustrate both the strengths and weaknesses of trait analysis. Finally, the authors deftly point out in several places how the specialized jargon developed by some stream and river ecologists may actually impede understanding and effective communication. Chapters 8 and 9 are devoted to ecosystem ecology (Running waters as ecosystems: Metabolism, energy and carbon, Running waters as ecosystems: Nutrients). Here the authors provide authoritative and readable accounts of energy flow and nitrogen and phosphorous cycling in rivers and streams with a particular emphasis on downstream transport and terrestrial-aquatic linkages.

The book finishes with Chapter 10 which is focused on reciprocal interactions between humans with stream and river ecosystems, although this topic is also foreshadowed in many places throughout this forward-looking book. Here the authors provide timely and concise reviews of relevant topics, examples being “the invasional meltdown” (rampant replacement of native biota with alien and invasive species), biodiversity losses, effects of the interconnection of river basins, new and emerging contaminants, and the consequences of on-going climate change. Hildrew & Giller also provide guarded predictions about how stream and river ecosystems may be affected by climate change, bringing an element of urgency regarding the need for accelerating the development of solution-oriented knowledge while simultaneously fostering a widespread awareness of the scale of the effects of human activities on freshwater ecosystems worldwide. The statistics regarding the geographical scope of the effects of basin linkage, invasive species, and water abstraction, for example, will likely be truly astonishing to many readers of this book. It is not all doom and gloom, however, as the authors document a significant number of river ecosystems that have shown remarkable improvements in water quality and recovery of diversity through human intervention. Although I personally am most inspired by questions concerning basic biology and ecology, as provided in the previous nine chapters, I found Chapter 10 to be absolutely riveting and I believe that it will likely be the most important contribution of this textbook.

In summary, this is an excellent book that was a pleasure to read. Here and there the writing was enlivened by a delightful whimsy that itself hints at the high level of inspiration and excitement that so obviously drove Hildrew & Giller to their writing desks. *The Biology and Ecology of Streams and Rivers* should be considered an essential desk reference for all stream and river ecologists and should be required reading for all undergraduate and graduate classes that focus on freshwater ecology.

Prof. Alexander D. Huryn

huryn@ua.edu

Department of Biological Sciences
University of Alabama
Tuscaloosa, Alabama, U.S.A. 35487

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11368352>